

REIMAGINING HR PRACTICES TO FOSTER ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND
JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

In the age of swift and dramatic technological disruption, workforce development and training systems must respond just as swiftly and dramatically to ensure that all incumbent and future workers have access to quality employment throughout their careers. Technology will continue to change the way that we work, requiring workers to continuously learn new skills, adapt to new workplace technologies, and even new work environments. However, today's infrastructure for training and supporting current and future workers is not prepared to meet the rapidly changing needs of workers and employers that this technological change brings about. To sustain or enhance effectiveness organizations have to anticipate and monitor such changes and figure out how to deal with them. Moreover, though an organization must do strategic analysis to respond to such changes it must also implement strategic redirection. The implementation of strategic changes ultimately derives from the many small changes people make in their behavior, including the suggestions they offer for how best to implement a new strategy. This study will be an attempt to connect OCB to larger frameworks past and present of organizational theory. OCB is important and in this study we will explore OCB with well-established classic and modern concepts of organization.

Keywords: HR practices, Organizational commitment behavior, job satisfaction, organizational behavior

OCB

Various immediate and circuitous precursors of OCB have been recognized in examinations to date (e.g., Michel, 2017; Organ and Ryan, 1995; Smith, Organ, and Almost, 1983). In spite of the fact that occupation configuration is a vital HRM device (cf. Hernaus, 2016), Shantz, Alfes, Bracket, and Soane (2013) featured the lack of exploration on its suggestions on an assortment of execution results, including OCB. As far as we know, not many examination have inspected the immediate connection between formal work elements and representative city ways of behaving (e.g., Park, 2018; Todd & Kent, 2006). Consequently, a more profound perception of the hidden cycles that make sense of how different work qualities —, for example, work requests and occupation assets — convert into citizenship ways of behaving that are focused on the two people and associations is required. High work assets and requesting position necessities permit representatives to at the same time feel roused and energized, which thus expands their inspiration for work (Tadi, Bakker, and Oerlemans, 2015). As per Khan et al. (2012), there are a few parts of word related satisfaction, like remuneration and headway, associations with colleagues and bosses, work security and working circumstances, and components of work and execution. Work satisfaction goes about as a scaffold between these parts. JS was believed by numerous OCB studies to be a potential sign, and these examinations tracked down proof to help the previously

mentioned ensure (Dalal, 2005; LePine et al., 2002; Murphy et al., 2002; Organ and Ryan, 1995). There aren't numerous clarifications for the JS and OCB's helpful way of behaving, yet one of them fixates on the correspondence standard (Cialdini, 2001; Gouldner, 1960) and social exchange hypothesis (Cropanzano and Greenberg, 1997). Khan et al. (2012) recognized various elements that add to work related satisfaction, including pay and advancement amazing open doors, associations with colleagues and chiefs, employer stability and working circumstances, as well as the genuine work itself. Satisfaction at work fills in as a connection between these components. Various OCB examinations respected JS to be a possible pointer, and these investigations found information to back up the previously mentioned ensure (Dalal, 2005; LePine et al., 2002; Murphy et al., 2002; Organ and Ryan, 1995). There aren't many purposes behind the JS and OCB's agreeable way of behaving, yet one of them is around the correspondence standard and social exchange hypothesis (Cialdini, 2001; Gouldner, 1960). (Cropanzano and Greenberg, 1997). Khan et al. (2012) distinguished various components, including pay and headway possibilities, associations with colleagues and managers, professional stability and working circumstances, as well as the genuine work itself, that add to work related satisfaction. The association between these parts is given by work satisfaction. JS was viewed as a potential sign by numerous OCB examinations, and these examinations tracked down proof to help the previously mentioned confirmation (Dalal, 2005; LePine et al., 2002; Murphy et al., 2002; Organ and Ryan, 1995).

2.1 Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction is normally perceived to connect with an individual's feelings of satisfaction while at work, which act as a main impetus to work. Brief and Weiss (2002); Cost (2004; Roa, (2005); Robbins (2005); Value; Roa, (2005). The satisfaction of the gig is a higher priority than vanity, joy, or happiness. As per Howard and Frink (1996) and Wayne (1996), Job Satisfaction is a complicated idea that incorporates representative opinions in regards to a scope of both characteristic and outward work factors (2006). As per Lyord (2000), this is a specialist's overall demeanor about their work. It alludes to how much people like (are happy with) or hate (are disappointed with) their business. Physiological and mental requirements are utilized by the gig holder to check their level of fulfillment, as per Betts' (2000) meaning of work satisfaction. Any association's capacity to succeed relies upon its kin, the two chiefs and adherents, and how they feel about their work. Keychain (2003) noticed that when representatives are satisfied with their business, the work environment is more useful. Since satisfaction diminished pressure and vulnerability, it further developed direction. Also, in light of the fact that cheerful staff serve buyers much better, new clients are attracted to them. Keychain (2003) stressed further that satisfied specialists display elevated degrees of occupation fulfillment because of their feeling of having a place with the organization. As per the work attributes model created by Hackman and Oldham in 1974, Job Satisfaction is impacted by five crucial work qualities. Autonomy, criticism, expertise variety, task character, and undertaking significance have been perceived as the five principal business viewpoints. Perceiving position characteristics and what they mean for laborers' Job Satisfaction inside an organization is vital. The great effect achieved by the presence of occupation fulfillment supposedly is building up and goes about as an inspiration for a representative to keep doing the undertaking relegated, adding to hierarchical success. Employee Job Satisfaction has provoked the curiosity of hierarchical researchers for a long time. Business fulfillment alludes to how satisfied an individual is with their work (Rajat, 2009). In their review, Gupta and Joshi (2008) reached the resolution that Job Satisfaction is a vital procedure for empowering representatives to invest more energy. Job Satisfaction, as per Gupta and Joshi (2008), is urgent since most people spend a huge part

of their lives at work. At the point when representatives are cheerful in their positions and thus offer better support, they have better impressions of the organization's labor and products. (2011) Bontis, Richards, and Serenko. The Work Qualities Model (JCM), created by Cost and Muller in 1986, has gotten most of the study support for its legitimacy as a proportion of the number of different activities that are expected to finish a work, every one of which requires the utilization of a scope of a representative's capacities and gifts. Task character, as per Coelho and Augusto (2010), advances that one's work is helpful and critical, which thus spurs one to perform well. Hackman and Oldham (1974) characterized task significance as the degree to which a task essentially influences the lives or work of others, whether inside the prompt association or in the outside world. According to Hackman and Oldham (1974), independence is the degree to which a task gives the representative adaptability, freedom, and decision in orchestrating their work and picking the techniques to be utilized to make it happen. It is the expansion in representative opportunity, dynamic power, and vertical obligation. Coelho and Augusto (2010) guarantee that independence might urge and engage laborers to endeavor new things, gain from their missteps, and utilize their space-explicit capacities. (Overall, across all occupations, 47% of people surveyed said they were satisfied with their work, and 33% said they were very content with their positions. As per research, Job Satisfaction is altogether corresponded with the situational factors independence, criticism, expertise variety, task character, and errand importance (Noor Azzah and Rudzi, 2007). As indicated by Spector and Jex (1991), there is a moderate connection between impression of work highlights and occupation fulfillment, with a scope of 0 to 0 and 32 to 46. To assist representatives with acknowledging what should be changed and to have superior information on the idea of their work, top administration ought to give input. As indicated by research by Coelho and Augusto (2010), Job Satisfaction is altogether related with the situational variables of independence, input, expertise variety, task personality, and errand pertinence (Anderson, 1984; Colarelli, Dignitary and Konstans, 1987). Moreover, Noor Azzah and Rudzi (2007) found a significant connection between Job Satisfaction and the situational variables of independence, criticism, expertise variety, task character, and errand importance (Noor Azzah and Rudzi, 2007). Correlational non-trial research was utilized in the review. The organization's site gave the example edge to this examination. The site, which gathers a rundown of drive-thru eateries open in Shah Alam, Selangor, is referred to as one wellspring of data. The administrators of the singular eateries were by and by reached to approve the all out number of cheap food outlets to guarantee the legitimacy and dependability of the example outline. The all out number of supervisors utilized by drive-through joints with areas in Shah Alam filled in as the review's populace. Since it is connected to numerous regions of their work and those that take up most of their time — settling client issues and questions — work fulfillment is viewed as an exceptionally fundamental issue inside the help area, especially for call focus firms. To ensure adequacy in doing their undertakings and occupations, representatives should in this way feel content and settled in their workplaces. To increment work joy and execution, this examination means to pinpoint the business includes that make occupations more fascinating in authoritative contexts. The thought of occupation fulfillment is one that has drawn in the consideration of specialists and has been the subject of various examinations since one of the significant elements add to uncommon work execution, and on the grounds that low work fulfillment may likewise cause specific problems or mental issues. One of the key components that keeps an elevated degree of execution is work fulfillment, a point that has been read up for over 50 years and is still of progressing interest today. The vital driver of this interest might be the impacts of work fulfillment on activities connected with efficiency, non-appearance, representative relations, turnover, execution, and responsibility (Eyupoglu and Saner, 2009). (Darrat, Amyx, and Bennett, 2010). The Hawthorne review (1924-1933), fundamentally credited to Elton Mayo

of the Harvard Business college, tried to research the impacts of different circumstances (most remarkably light) on specialists' efficiency. These investigations are viewed as one of the main commitments to the investigation of occupation fulfillment. Some cases that Maslow's hypothesis of necessities ordered progression, hypothesis of inspiration, and hypothesis of occupation fulfillment laid out the preparation for one another. As indicated by this thought, people endeavor to satisfy the five prerequisites recorded above: physiological necessities, security needs, social requirements, confidence requirements, and self-completion needs. This worldview gives a strong groundwork to the improvement of early hypotheses of work fulfillment (Gupta, 2009).

2.2. Recruitment and selection

According to Ryan and Ployhart (2014), researchers and HR professionals are familiar with the concept of recruitment and selection. The company's suggested goals and management systems now include the HR department as its foundation (Derous & Fruyt, 2016). The main goal of the recruitment and selection process is to fill open positions with knowledgeable, qualified personnel at the lowest possible cost. The right team of personnel is required to meet the company's goals (Fong, Ooi, Tan, Lee, & Chong, 2011).

The HR policy needs to follow the company's business strategies (Singh, 2004). Organizations must therefore maintain a balance between the recruitment and selection processes.

When managers must decide whether to hire new employees for their organisations, this is one of the most important phases of the recruitment and selection process. According to Chapman and Webster (2003), the recruitment and selection process should be broken down into four stages: (i) the advertisement strategy; (ii) accepting applications; (iii) basic screening of applicants; and (iv) the final choice. While the selection process is carefully hiring the proper persons for the job, recruitment is the act of gathering names of potential candidates for the position.

The HR policy needs to follow the company's business strategies (Singh, 2004). Organizations must therefore maintain a balance between their hiring and selection processes and their HR policies. The majority of large businesses rely largely on formal methods and bureaucratic procedures used by professionals in their HR departments (Lockyer & Scholarios, 2004). Successful businesses, according to Darrag and Mohamed (2010), should embrace fundamental methods to hiring that will draw in the best candidates. Additionally, the recruiting and selection process in detail affects employee morale and represents the system used by different firms for recruitment and selection (Loganathan & Dharmaraj, 2017).

H1a: Recruitment and Selection has a significant positive impact on OC.

H1b: The relationship of Recruitment and Selection and OC is mediated by Job Satisfaction.

2.3. Training

Employee training attempts to improve employees' skill and capacity for executing a certain task. Given that employees are considered to be valuable resources by companies, businesses spend in their training programmes to increase the knowledge and potential of their staff members (Jimenez & Valle, 2012). The purpose of training is to fundamentally remove any barrier that exists between the workforce's potential and the requirements of the workplace. With the right training, the personnel's behaviour and performance can be improved. To improve the comprehension and expertise of the company's

employees, training and advancement are necessary. According to Lamba and Choudhary (2013), the training provided to employees—which includes instruction in job orientation, safety, and promotional activities—is intended to increase the HR's level of knowledge and increase their effectiveness. Enhancing skills through training and fostering a sense of fulfilment in a career contribute to a sense of security about the future and support the growth of self-efficacy (Guest, 2017). The goal of the training programmes is to increase employee productivity toward the organisation. The training programmes are led by qualified managers of the same companies or can be recruited from other agencies. However, Maheshwari and Vohra (2015) came to the conclusion that training gives employees the skills to improve their comprehension of organisational procedures and raise their OC. A strong correlation between training and OC has been shown by numerous studies (Bisharat et al., 2017; Obeidat et al., 2014; Paşaoğlu, 2015). Following that, the study will test the following assumptions based on the discussion:

H2a: Training has a very favourable effect on OC.

H2b: Job satisfaction acts as a mediator in the relationship between training and organisational commitment.

2.4. Rewards and recognition

HR managers are always looking for standardised solutions so they can properly reward and acknowledge their employees' accomplishments (Campbell-Allen, Houston, & Mann, 2008). A reward framework should be a package or structure that includes perks like pay, leaves, medical reimbursements, transportation reimbursements, and commissions for the firms' employees. When workers are confident in the benefits and accolades they will receive, they will be more motivated to work. Because it can raise employees' motivation to work, a good reward system and compensation structure are crucial for boosting productivity, efficiency, and the competitiveness of the business (Lawler, 1990). Rewards play a significant part in fostering and maintaining dedication within the workforce, as well as ensuring that employees' competence and commitment are upheld, according to Malhotra, Budhwar, and Prowse (2007).

The company's incentive programme offers a plethora of advantages. The company's compensation system is based on performance, experience, qualifications, and seniority. Benefits include overtime pay and transportation, medical, and mobile allowances (Lim & Ling, 2012). For the workforce to successfully complete their goals and objectives, they must understand the justification for incentive allocation. A great sense of pleasure would result in better commitment at work if employees participated in suggesting their own ideas for rewards and recognition (Milne, 2007).

Furthermore, Kooij, Jansen, Dijkers, and Lange (2010) found a strong association between commitment and job satisfaction and the reward dimension of HR policies (including perks). However, Meyer and Becker (2004) found that once HR techniques were applied, employees' engagement increased because they felt more appreciated and had more autonomy. Numerous academics have demonstrated a strong link between organisational commitment and rewards and recognition (Chew & Chan, 2008; Obeidat et al., 2014). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the following hypotheses:

H3a: The influence of reward and recognition on OC is quite favourable.

H3b: Job Satisfaction acts as a mediator in the link between Reward and Recognition and OC.

2.5. Performance appraisal satisfaction

Effective performance appraisal framework is a medium for improving the OC (Behery & Paton, 2008). Companies, according to Chen and Eldridge (2010), are reportedly paying close attention to a certain HR practise, namely the impact of performance appraisal satisfaction on the company's accomplishments. It is a planned process that evaluates each employee's performance in terms of their assets and weaknesses. Boice and Kleiner (1997) framed a performance appraisal method that showed the worker's performance as well as their dedication, and Whiting, Kline, and Sulsky (2008) supported this notion. The effect of performance appraisals (PA) on workers' job satisfaction was examined by Kampkötter (2017). His research revealed some extremely intriguing findings that showed PA has a significantly significant favourable impact on job satisfaction.

According to Whiting et al. (2008), it is challenging to copy and move the appraisal systems around the companies. Using the performance evaluation method, Sripirabaa and Krishnaveni (2009) have inferred conclusions concerning organisational decisions including compensation and promotion. It is obvious that high levels of Job Satisfaction and OC will be attained if the employees are aware that they are being fairly evaluated. Researchers Lim and Ling (2012) studied the HR practises of contractors and found that while there is a strong association between Job Satisfaction and Performance Appraisal System, employees are persuaded by its methodology. As a result, based on the foregoing discussion, this study aims to test the following theories:

H4a: OC is much benefited by performance appraisal satisfaction.

H4b: Job satisfaction acts as a mediator in the link between Performance Appraisal Satisfaction and OC.

2.7. Work Environment

According to Danish, Ramazan, and Ahmad (2013), the workplace is the environment employees work in when they are employed by a company. To be successful, businesses should design their workplaces in a way that increases the degree of commitment and inspiration among their employees, which will ultimately produce the best results. In contrast to those who feel otherwise, employees who have positive workplace attitudes are more likely to work more ardently and value their work environment, according to Khuong and Vu (2014). Administrators should improve the workplace in this way to ensure the welfare and comfort of their staff. Previous research reveals that a workplace can be evaluated from a variety of angles.

According to Hanaysha and Tahir's (2016) proposal, the workplace should include elements like participation, group union, administrator assistance, assignment introduction, work clarity, self-sufficiency, innovation, development, physical comfort, and administrative control. Workplace metrics identified by James and James (1989) include "work challenge, work self-governance, pioneer work assistance, and importance, fairness, and value of the incentive framework. Therefore, the workplace can be estimated in terms of any aspect that affects a worker's behaviour in their relationship. According to research by Ferraris, Erhardt, and Bresciani (2017), ambidextrous work presents new difficulties for HRM. Their study was grounded in a qualitative methodology in a European setting. In seven global corporations, managers were interviewed in twenty-one instances. Different HRM systems are created to facilitate ambidextrous work, according to the research.

Numerous studies revealed that the job has a notable positive impact on OC. According to Hanaysha and Tahir (2016) and Khuong and Vu (2014) before them, a more attractive work environment has a positive impact on job satisfaction. Additionally, it is clear that the workplace has a significant impact on hierarchical responsibility. Hanaysha (2016) asserts that one of the fundamental tenets of OC is the workplace. In light of the aforementioned literature, the following hypotheses will be investigated in this study:

H5a: The work environment significantly improves OC.

H5b: Job Satisfaction acts as a mediator in the link between Work Environment and OC.

2.7. Mediating variable: Job satisfaction

Numerous locations around the world have conducted in-depth studies on the relationship between HR practises and work satisfaction. The needs of the employees in terms of work environment and assessments, management styles, and employment prospects that result in commitment toward the business were identified by several researchers as job satisfaction (Robinson & Rousseau, 1994; Zhao, Wayne, Glibkowski, & Bravo, 2007). The two phenomena that govern job happiness are first, experiences, and second, job belief (Weiss, 2002). A worker's behaviour and response to a certain task can also be used to describe job satisfaction. The responses could be favourable or unfavourable.

Suma and Lesha (2013) did a study in the public sector in the municipality of Shkoder, and their findings indicated that contentment with pay, work, and supervision quality had a favourable impact on the OC. Other researches have also affirmed a strong connection between job satisfaction and OC (Chen, 2007; Liu & Norcio, 2008). Del Giudice, Carayannis, and Della Peruta (2012) emphasised that an employee's behaviour and abilities are closely related to the culture to which they belong and that it is crucial to understand the benefits and drawbacks of each culture. Finding a cultural fit is more difficult the more extreme the cultural disparities. According to Schalk and Roe's (2007) theory, employees will be highly committed if they have a positive perspective of their work and the organisation. The mediating role of job satisfaction in psychological contract breach (PCB) and organisational commitment (OC) was further examined and validated by Antonaki and Trivellas (2014).

The current study is distinctive in that it examines the mediated relationship between HR procedures and OC among Indian employees working in the telecommunications industry. The study's framework, which is based on the discussion above, is shown below.

3. Research design

Data collection was done via convenience sampling. The survey was completed using the self-administered survey method. Using Smart PLS 3, partial least-squares structural equation modelling was done to investigate the connections between HR practises and OC. Using a typology developed by Zhao, Lynch, and Chen, this study also examined whether Job Satisfaction mediates the association between HR practises and OC (2010).

Table 1. Variables and their sources		
Variables	No. of items	Source
Organizational commitment	6	Saks (2006)
Recruitment and	5	Edgar and Geare (2005)

selection		
Training	6	Karatepeand Vatankhah (2014)
Reward and recognition	6	Kinnie, Hutchinson, Purcell, Rayton and Swart (2005) and Kooij et al. (2010)
Performance appraisal satisfaction	6	Kuvaas (2006)
Work environment	10	Morgesonand Humphrey (2006) and Hanaysha (2016)
Job satisfaction	4	Hanayshaand Tahir (2016)

3.1. Instrument design

The information about the pre-established scales this study used to measure each latent variable in the suggested theoretical framework is provided in Table 1. (Figure 1).

3.2. Research methodology

White-collar, low-level, and mid-level employees of four distinct telecommunication companies operating in Bhubaneswar were the sources of the data. These businesses have all been operating in India for more than 5 years and control the vast bulk of the market. Over 1000 people were employed by each enterprise in Indian. It was confirmed from these businesses' websites that they choose their staff in accordance with appropriate HR procedures, both at a managerial and technical level of the degree of client service. Each chosen firm's HR managers were contacted by phone as part of the data collection procedure to ask for their participation in conducting the survey in their individual firms. After ensuring the respondents' and the companies' confidentiality, they were told of the study's goal and methodology. To the best of our knowledge, the link to the survey was emailed to the HR managers, who subsequently disseminated it without bias to the managerial-level staff members and customer service representatives. To achieve the highest possible response rate, a reminder email was sent to the HR managers after a week.

Prior to data collection, a self-administered pilot study was carried out using 40 replies (10 responses from each firm) that were gathered by the researcher visiting the head offices of the firms. The questionnaires were somewhat modified once the pilot study was finished in order to increase their validity and readability. The final form of the questionnaire was then distributed to each company in order to collect data from them.

		Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	159	73
	Female	59	27
Marital status	Married	122	56
	Unmarried	96	44
Age	Below 30 years	94	43
	30–35 years	63	29

	36–40 years	39	18
	41 year and above	22	10
Education	Graduate	50	23
	Post graduate	129	59
	Above post graduate	39	18
Job designation	Manager	28	13
	Assistant/executive manager	35	16
	Customer service officer	155	71
Years of experience	3 and below	46	21
	4–6	122	56
	7–9	35	16
	10 and above	15	7

315 employees in total were contacted to take the survey. 250 employees did, however, actively participate in completing the survey. Out of these, 218 replies (or 87.2% of the total) were screened out as being comprehensive, usable, and lacking no information. According to Bentler & Chou (1987) and Siddiqui, (2013) at least 15 examples of each measured variable or indicator are required for SEM. A further guideline is to use five instances for each parameter estimate (Stevens, 2002). A sample size of 218 looked logically justified in view of the aforementioned claims. Table 2 presents specifics about the responder profile. Overall, the sample can be regarded as consisting of workers that were well educated, youthful, and had only held their current position for a brief period of time.

4.Results

4.1.Results of measurement model (CFA results)

According to Table 3, the composite reliability for all of the latent variables is higher than the advised range of 0.7, proving divergent validity (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 1998). Additionally, it can be determined that all of the variables' AVE values are higher than the threshold of 0.5, suggesting that the explained variance exceeds the unexplained variance and confirming the study's convergent validity. Hetero-trait Mono-trait (HTMT) ratio, which has a recommended range of being less than 0.9, was used to assess the discriminant validity (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Table 4's results show that every value for the HTMT ratio across all latent variables is less than 0.9, indicating that the correlation between the indicators across variables is lower than the correlation between the indicators within the same latent variable. As a result, discriminant validity was also established.

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value was 0.076, and a value less than 0.08 is typically taken as a sign of a successful model fit (Hu & Bentler, 1998). As a result, the results showed that there was little difference between the observed and suggested correlation mix.

The NFI (Normed Fit Index) value of 0.92 showed that the study's theoretical model held up well overall and delivered a good fit. Indicating that there was no multi-collinearity and that all of the values of the VIF coefficient were less than 5, this was a good sign for continuing with the mediation study. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), which eliminated all the components with loadings below 0.7, was used to evaluate the measurement model. Table 5 presents the CFA findings in summary.

4.2.Results of structural model (path analysis)

The findings of the route analysis are presented in Table 6, which shows a generally significant positive association between an organization's HR procedures and its employees' job satisfaction. The results of the path analysis show that Reward and Recognition (= 0.208, p 0.05) and the work environment (= 0.184, p 0.1) offered to the employee to perform their services have the largest effects on OC. The hypotheses H3 and H5 were therefore accepted. Table 5's results also show that the satisfaction with recruitment and selection (= 0.176, p 0.1) and performance appraisals (= 0.173, p 0.05) have a significant and direct impact on OC. Our findings support earlier research by Endodu et al. (2013) and Paul and Anantharaman (2004), which found a strong beneficial link between OC and HRM practises such development-oriented appraisal and thorough training.

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Mean (SD)
Recruitment and selection	0.881	0.881	0.597	4.20(0.321)
Organizational commitment	0.909	0.909	0.625	3.95(0.214)
Performance appraisal satisfaction	0.839	0.839	0.566	3.41(0.109)
Reward and recognition	0.851	0.852	0.534	4.65(0.301)
Training	0.929	0.928	0.720	3.45(0.051)
Work environment	0.916	0.915	0.642	4.59(0.217)
Job satisfaction	0.816	0.965	0.542	3.84(0.106)

Table 4. HTMT ratio results: discriminant validity						
	Recruitment and selection	Organizational commitment	Performance appraisal satisfaction	Reward and recognition	Training	Work environment
Recruitment and selection						
Organizational commitment	0.712					
Performance appraisal satisfaction	0.841	0.715				
Reward and recognition	0.809	0.709	0.717			
Training	0.195	0.331	0.187	0.202		
Work environment	0.467	0.518	0.477	0.491	0.606	

The outcomes of the mediation analysis are shown in Table 7. Previous research has revealed that the association between HR practices and OC is mediated by job satisfaction (Antonaki & Trivellas, 2014). In India's service sector, little research has been done at the person level. The findings show that the relationship between recruitment and selection, training, the work environment, and OC is mediated complementarity by job satisfaction. It's interesting to note that, despite not having a direct effect on OC, there is a relationship between the two when Job Satisfaction acts as a mediator.

Although the mediator selected fits in well with the theoretical model, complementary mediation refers to the possibility of an excluded mediator, which this study does not include (Zhao et al., 2010). As a result, the statistical findings support H1b, H2b, and H5b; however, H2a was statistically rejected.

Table 5. Summary of confirmatory factor analysis						
	Recruitment and selection	Organizational commitment	Performance appraisal satisfaction	Reward and recognition	Training	Work environment
WE1						0.875
WE2						0.845
WE3						0.751
WE4						0.817
WE5						0.768

WE6						0.743
PAS1			0.761			
PAS2			0.730			
PAS4			0.755			
PAS5			0.763			
OC1		0.781				
OC2		0.796				
OC3		0.760				
OC4		0.843				
OC5		0.785				
OC6		0.778				
RR1				0.729		
RR2				0.744		
RR4				0.740		
RR5				0.711		
RR6				0.731		
RS1	0.780					
RS2	0.788					

Results also show that Job satisfaction only partially mediates the connection between OC and performance appraisal. This indicates that the mediator picked is suitable and effectively fits the theoretical model. The statistical findings support H4b as a result. The findings show that, on the contrary, job satisfaction is not a mediating factor in the association between rewards and recognition and organizational culture. Therefore, regardless of an employee's degree of contentment, higher rewards—both monetary and non—are likely to have a greater impact on his level of loyalty to the company. This discovery persuades us to embrace H3b. Overall, the findings show that adopting sound HR practices in a company results in more devoted and contented workers. Thus, it can be inferred that job satisfaction and dedication are intangible qualities that staff members notice and that are crucial to keeping them on the job (Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003; Hashim, 2010).

5. Analysis and recommendations

Through the mediating effect of job satisfaction, we theoretically and empirically deduce in this study that HR practises are associated with OC both directly and indirectly. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this is one of few studies—and the first large-scale, systematic study—that looks at the relationship between "HR practices-Organizational Commitment" on an individual level in India's telecom industry. Additionally, a development in this area is the function of Job Satisfaction as a bridge between HRM methods and OC. A thorough analysis of earlier research found that the service industry has not received the proper attention in relation to the role of HR practises and their impact on the OC.

This study tested a favourable association between the employees' opinions of the use of proper HR practises and stronger OC, as well as a high level of job satisfaction, using the lens of social exchange theory. Particularly, it was discovered that the respondents' OC level was favourably correlated with the high commitment HR procedures connected to Recruitment and Selection, Rewards and Recognition,

and Work Environment. It may be inferred that professionals should pay close attention to the effective application of HR practises, rules, and procedures because doing so results in the workforce developing favourable work attitudes.

Our analysis demonstrates that while training does not directly affect OC, it does result in higher levels of satisfaction, which in turn encourages employees to pursue better organisational goals. Since the majority of the employees in our sample are young and have worked for the company for a shorter period of time, they prioritise receiving sufficient training, which increases their level of satisfaction. This level of pleasure encourages people to become more committed to the company over the long run. This supports the contention made by Absar, Azim, Balasundaram, and Akhter (2010) that effective training and development do have a favourable impact on an employee's level of satisfaction.

Additionally, the results of this study show that Job Satisfaction does not function as a mediator between Rewards and OC. The possible explanation for this is that mid-level managers and officers in Asian Emerging Economies often face challenges like a lack of suitable employment opportunities, weak job security or financial constraints, or being the family's sole breadwinner. As a result, a higher level of reward system may persuade employees to remain with the company even if they are dissatisfied with their current positions.

India is one of the emerging and developing nations with economies that strive to market their goods and provide exceptional services. This study deepens our understanding of Indian white-collar workers' attitudes toward their jobs. Our findings demonstrate how the various aspects of job satisfaction might act as a mediator in the interactions between OC and the HR procedures used by businesses. According to Abbas Al-Refaie (2015), increasing employee happiness is the only way to increase a sense of belonging to the organisation, which in turn motivates workers to work toward achieving organisational objectives. Based on our research, we have presented concrete theoretical frameworks and practical advice to assist such organisations in better understanding the critical determinant of OC in terms of HR practises.

Justifying the Hypothesis

The research led to adoption of positive recruitment and selection practices that in turn associated positively with organizational commitment and support formation of H1a hypothesis. It was also found that job satisfaction stepped in as a mediator to the association between recruitment and selection measures and organizational commitment (verifying H1b). Figures showed that despite the motivation and engagement not being the main positive impact of the training directly, they led to higher levels of job satisfaction, which moved towards commitment to the organization. Thus, result confirms hypothesis H2b, indicating training is the mediated variable in the organizational commitment and job satisfaction relationship. On the contrary, hypothesis H2a that training has the significant role in advancing organizational commitment was considered invalid from the statistical side.

The research proved a statistical meaningful and positive relationship between rewards and recognition practices as well as willingness follow the organization's decisions, which is a manner under H3a hypothesis. Job satisfaction did not play part between the relationship between rewards and recognition and organizational commitment, this is why we have failed to get the conclusion of hypothesis H3b. It was found that job performance appraisal satisfaction had an important and direct effect on organizational commitment which was evidence of H4a proposition. Besides, job satisfaction was also

partially a mediator variable between performance appraisal satisfaction and organizational commitment and the hypothesis H4b was sure to be confirmed.

On the other hand, the work settings were shown to exert a large positive impact on job involvement, forming the basis for the support of hypothesis H5a. Moreover, job satisfaction acted as nucleus between the environment and the organizational commitment of the employee, thus, verifying hypothesis H5b. Finally, the study is able to provide reinforcement on most of the hypotheses, showing that HR practices take center stage in making employees to be loyal to their employer, either directly or indirectly through the effect of job satisfaction.

6. Management and conceptual implications

One of the sectors in India with the fastest growth is telecommunications. Customer service interactions are a crucial component of the whole customer experience, which HR managers in the service industries must comprehend. Therefore, it is important to maintain the employee's long-term OC at its highest possible level in order to maximize job satisfaction and motivation. In order to guarantee an excellent customer experience, organizations should make every effort to build a highly motivated and devoted team. These service-oriented businesses routinely explore strategies that help them maintain their competitive edge. Telecom firms should pay additional attention to policies and processes that limit employees' ability to perform, which in turn lowers employee satisfaction. Therefore, managers should implement and improve their HR processes with great care, which further results in increased OC. HR managers should focus on HRM procedures during recruiting and selection, implementation of appropriate training, performance appraisal processes, and creation of a work environment that is conducive to productivity.

This study supports the social exchange hypothesis, which states that when corporations express their intention to engage in social exchange relationships by investing in HR systems This study supports the social exchange theory, which states that when businesses invest in HR practices to demonstrate their desire to engage in social exchange relationships, employees respond by developing a greater sense of empathy for the goals of the business and reciprocating with actions that are advantageous to the business.

7. Future guidelines and restrictions

The Bhubaneswar area's telecommunications sector was the focus of this investigation. In order to investigate a more holistic approach and explore such a well-integrated HR practice-commitment model, researchers can expand their investigations to different contexts and economies in the future. This will increase the degree of generalizability. Furthermore, when these associations are examined in the context of SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises) and large-scale firms, future researchers might do a comparative analysis to determine if the results differ.

The information was compiled using a convenience sample from India's telecom industry. Therefore, a bigger sample size would provide a more accurate picture of the effects of HR procedures on employee commitment levels. Future studies can include moderators and control factors to see if the connections change depending on the respondent's age, education level, occupation, and other characteristics.

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